

ORCID of the Journal: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-0723-9485>

DOI Number of the Paper: <https://zenodo.org/records/12611875>

Edition Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities JARH, 4\(2\) April-June 2024](#)

Link of the Paper: <https://jar.bwo-researches.com/index.php/jarh/article/view/485>

HJRS Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities JARH \(HEC-Recognized for 2023-2024\)](#)

REGISTER VARIATION IN PAKISTANI ENGLISH POLITICAL DISCOURSE: AN INSTIGATION OF TWITTER ANALYTICS USING BIBER'S MULTIDIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS

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Paper Information

Citation of the paper:

(JARH) Rashid, S. Mahmood, B., Sarfraz, Z., (2024). Register Variation in Pakistani English Political Discourse: An Instigation of Twitter Analytics Using Biber's Multidimensional Analysis. In *Journal of Academic Research for Humanities*, 4(2), 221–230.

Subject Areas for JARH:

- 1 Humanities
- 2 English

Timeline of the Paper at JARH:

Received on: 02-06-2024
 Reviews Completed: 15-06-2024
 Accepted on: 28-06-2024
 Online on: 29-06-2024.

License:

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Recognized for BWO-R:

Published by BWO Researches INTL.:

DOI Image of the paper:

Abstract

The current study used multidimensional analysis to investigate written political discourse in Pakistani English, which significantly advances the discipline of linguistics. A corpus of language data is analyzed using a method known as multidimensional analysis to identify and investigate linguistic features. The study employs Biber's (1988) multidimensional analysis using D1 and D5 of the multidimensional approach to investigate how the language of Pakistani tweets holds the official language. In his multidimensional approach, Biber addresses textual information and genre in two of his six dimensions, D1 and D5, respectively. The study was carried out by analyzing data from a corpus of Pakistani English tweets using MAT software (version 1.3). Because the technology allowed for the data to be categorized and analyzed, the researchers were able to identify and quantify linguistic elements. After that, these characteristics were investigated and qualitatively assessed using D1 and D2 from the multidimensional approach. The findings demonstrated the usage of D1 non-informational vocabulary in Pakistani English political literature. The significance of the study lies in its ability to illuminate the features of written discourse in Pakistani English, specifically concerning politics. The results of the investigation suggest that the language used in written political discourse, Pakistani English, is not the official language. The study also highlights the need for multidimensional analysis in understanding the nature of written discourse across genre and linguistic barriers. To sum up, the results of this study can significantly benefit the linguistics community and direct efforts towards language standardization.

Keywords: Illuminate, Tweets, Variation, English, Linguistic

Introduction

Language is a dynamic, ever-evolving tool that adapts to the political, social, and cultural contexts in which it is used. Because of Pakistan's distinct political climate, a wide range of cultural influences, and rich linguistic heritage, the English dialect spoken there, referred to as Pakistani English, has developed into a distinctive form of communication. Pakistani English is fascinating when it comes to registering distinctions in political discourse since it provides significant insights into the country's democratic processes, power relations, and socio-political trends. (Hussain, Rubab et. al. , 2023), Within Pakistan, English plays a major role in education, governance, and the media. As such, research on the political conversation in Pakistani English becomes very insightful and pertinent. In political communication, register variation—a linguistic notion that refers to the variety of language options available to speakers in various social situations—is crucial. (Tahira, Muhammad, Asma, 2023), It includes a broad range of linguistic elements that influence the development of a particular communicative style, such as syntax, pragmatics, rhetorical techniques, and vocabulary. These variances show historical settings, power relationships, and larger sociocultural standards in addition to a politician's speaking style. This essay proposes to discover and investigate the register variations used by politicians through a thorough research of political discourse in Pakistani English. This examination will cover the rhetorical techniques used, vocabulary choices made, syntax used, and discourse tactics applied.

Significance of the study

The study advances the subject of World English by enabling us to examine the syntax and purpose of political discourse in Pakistani English as it is expressed in tweets on Twitter. By examining and analyzing the register variation in Pakistani English political discourse, this article seeks to shed light on the

linguistic strategies and choices used by policymakers, politicians, and media representatives to shape public opinion, communicate their messages, and uphold or undermine established power structures. We can comprehend the intricate relationship between language and politics in Pakistan better by exploring this linguistic dimension. Political discourse provides politicians with an important forum for communicating their objectives, programs, and beliefs to the general public. Politicians aim to engage with their voters, mobilize support, and sway public opinion using language.

Research Objectives

The current study aims:

- 1.To analyze informational or involved content present in Pakistani tweets.
- 2.To determine the level of formality has been examined in political tweets of Pakistani English.
- 3.To show that MAD tagging is helpful in the analysis of written text in political discourse.

Research Questions

1. How much informational or involved content is present in Pakistani tweets?
2. How the level of formality has been examined in political tweets in Pakistani English?
3. Why MAD tagging is helpful in the analysis of written text in political discourse?

Literature Review

The study of Pakistani English has only been studied briefly, for nearly three decades. By employing the corpus approach, the researchers Mahmood, A. (2009) assembled corpora of Pakistani English and attempted to examine the distinctive features of Pakistani English (Mahmood A., 2009). The collection of Pakistani English corpora created the possibility for MD analyses of Pakistani English, and many studies on Pakistani English have been done by using this method. To analyze a corpus of 1351 Pakistani print advertisements, Shakir (2013) used the MD technique for the first time in Pakistan (Shakir, 2013). He says that Pakistani

print advertisements are more similar to written discourse than face-to-face interactions, which contradicts earlier claims made by other academics who conducted MD analyses in 1988. [Alvi et al. \(2016a\)](#) used the MD (1988) approach to compare British Press Editorials with 250 editorials from five of Pakistan's top English-language newspapers. Using MD analysis, Alvi et al. in (2016), investigated the linguistic diversity of editorials written in Pakistani across genders for Pakistani print media. A special-purpose corpus of 300 editorials from The Dawn and The News, Pakistan's two most prominent newspapers, has been collected by the researchers (150 from male and female writers, respectively). The researchers analyzed the male and female editorial features of Pakistani writers and they also contrasted the male and female editorial writings of Pakistan with British writers. The researchers conclude that both internal and external comparisons have shown variations. By using [Biber's, 1988](#)) MD model ([Ahmed & Mehmood, A, 2015](#)) compared British and Pakistani news coverage registers. The researchers assembled a corpus of 1.1 million words from the Pakistani News Corpus (PNC). Using Biber's (1988) MD model, Ahmad and Mahmood (2015b) examined linguistic variation among eight subcategories of press coverage in Pakistani print media ([Biber, 1988](#)). The researchers have used the New MD technique ([Biber, 2003](#)) to examine the new textual dimensions of Pakistani press coverage using a corpus of 2.3 million words of Pakistani news. Using the MD technique, ([Ali & Shakir, A, 2016](#)) examined the stylistic diversity among the genres of Pakistani fiction (59 Pakistani English novels and 182 Pakistani English short tales ([Azher & Mehmood, A, 2017](#)) Used the MD technique to compare the linguistic characteristics of academic discourses in British and Pakistani English ([Biber, 1988](#)) 8.38 million Words, from M.Phil. And Ph.D. dissertations in the three major academic fields of sciences, social sciences, and humanities, were analyzed

by the researchers. "Both Pakistani and British academic texts are found to be informative, non-narrative, explicit, non-persuasive, and indifferent," the researchers claim in their conclusion to their study. [Hussain et al. \(2016\)](#) used the New MD technique ([Biber, 2003](#)) to examine linguistic diversity among different Pakistani English registers (8 written and 4 spoken). The researchers chose the written and spoken Pakistani components of the International Corpus of English. The researchers studied the new textual dimensions in several spoken and written English registers used in Pakistan. The researchers have discovered four new textual dimensions: dimension one has been identified as "involved vs. informational purposes," dimension two as "objective vs. personal stance of evaluation," dimension three as "past events vs. present situation," and dimension four as "discourse production bounded by real-time production vs. discourse production for remote conditions. A wide range of linguistic features should be chosen for examination to conduct a thorough linguistic analysis of a register or language variety. The linguistic characteristics of a particular register are highlighted and identified by the quantitative relative distribution of linguistic qualities. A single register cannot accurately describe a language by looking at just one or two linguistic traits. For a thorough analysis of a variety of languages in several registers, a wide range of linguistic traits must be noted, and representative sample texts from each register should be included. This is feasible only through multidimensional analysis. "Linguistic study of texts and text types, as well as of style or registers, rather than of individual linguistic constructions" is the goal of the multidimensional method ([Hussain, Muhammad Asim Mahmood, & Musarat Azher, 2016](#)). This study uses a multifaceted technique to investigate Pakistani English (PWE) register variance. The study focuses on a 2.1 million-word general-purpose corpus with 29 registers.

According to the study, PWE registers differ greatly in all dimensions; the majority are explicit, non-narrative, informational, devoid of overt persuasion, and abstract informational speech. Informational character registers display explicit characters, whereas interactive character registers display situation-dependent characters (Abbas et al. 2020). Four elements of variance are identified through an analysis of online registrations in Pakistani English versus U.S. English: oral story, abstract informational focus, interactive focus on mental activities, and present and future activities. The findings indicate that whereas Pakistani registers provide abstract information, American English communicates narrative and emotions. Incorporating these registers into global English versions will require more research (Shakir & Deuber, 2018). This study uses multidimensional analysis to look at the linguistic variety and operation of well-known English-language Pakistani publications. It compares and contrasts the language used in political and opinionated news subgenres. The study does a five-dimensional text analysis using 7240 text samples gathered from five leading newspapers. The results show heterogenic outcomes in terms of language functionality for opinion-based and political news reporting. Opinion-based reporting is coherent, but political news often produces inconsistent outcomes. There are suggestions for practical implementation and instructional ramifications (Muzaffar, 2022). This study examines the linguistic functioning and variety of prominent English-language Pakistani newspapers using multidimensional analysis. It contrasts the linguistic traits of opinion-based and political news subgenres. The study gathers 7240 text samples from five top newspapers and does a five-dimensional text analysis. The results show heterogenic outcomes in terms of language functionality for opinion-based and political news reporting (Ahmad & Ali, 2019). Prior linguistic studies of the web have mostly concentrated on unique linguistic

characteristics of Internet language and novel Internet registers such as tweets, blogs, forums, and instant messages. Internet registries have been analyzed using Multi-Dimensional (MD) analysis, with an emphasis on fundamental grammatical elements. On the other hand, little is known about the entire spectrum of registers that may be discovered online as well as the linguistic variation patterns that exist within them. By examining the dimensions of linguistic variation on the searchable web and the similarities and differences between online registers, this study seeks to describe the patterns of linguistic variation among various registers using MD analysis (Biber & Egbert, 2016). This study examines linguistic variety in online language, including blogs, microblogs, emails, discussion postings, and opinion columns, using corpus-based analysis. An exploratory corpus of internet texts from 2006 to the present was examined for data. Four functional dimensions of online registers are identified by the study: complex statement of opinion, interactive discourse, past vs present orientation, and personal narrative focus versus descriptive (Titak & Roberson, 2013). The main topic of this article is whether or not comments on news articles on the internet resemble in-person conversations. Online remarks are frequently referred to as "conversations," with the consensus being that they are similar to "dialogue." Still, these hypotheses are not supported by empirical data. We use multi-dimensional analysis (MDA) techniques to thoroughly analyze register-relevant features of online news comments to provide an answer to this topic. In particular, we use MDA to characterize the linguistic characteristics of online comments and contrast them with conventional registers (e.g., academic writing, and face-to-face discussion) to determine what kind of comments they are. As a result, we use the Canadian section of the International Corpus of English as well as the SFU Opinion and Comments Corpus. We demonstrate that

comments made online resemble opinion pieces more than casual conversations (Ehret & Taboada, 2020). This chapter uses the dimensions of online registers from Titak and Roberson (2013) to investigate patterns of micro-level linguistic variation in a corpus of Facebook and Twitter posts. (Rai, Syed, 2023), We perform a multi-dimensional analysis on an online records corpus (N = 5,331,120 words) comprising topic-coded public Facebook and Twitter postings gathered between 2011 and 2016. Six categories are used to organize the texts within each domain: Personal, Politics, Business, Weather, Entertainment, and Sports. The overall Facebook and Twitter postings (as two linguistically distinct registers) as well as the themes inside and between these two registers exhibit considerable structural differences, according to the results (Original et al. 2017). With an emphasis on Chinese and American companies, the study investigates the language elements of CEOs' statements in corporate social responsibility (CSR) reports. Chinese CSR reports are more informationally packed, narrative, less situationally dependent, less explicit, and show fewer characteristics of stringent time-constrained informational elaboration, according to the research, which used Biber's multidimensional analysis. The primary linguistic components that exhibit these differences are demonstratives, adverbs, infinitives, modal verbs, first-person pronouns, the present tense in contrast to the past tense, and nominalizations. The results offer a methodical comprehension of leaders' communications and suggest useful applications for cross-border corporate communication (Zhang & Chen, 2024). This study looks at the linguistic characteristics of MOOC video lectures in China in English, exposing variance across several subject areas. The language is abstract, formally planned, overtly referential, non-narrative, and has a low persuasive power. The results could be useful for MOOC instructors and instructional designers, particularly in nations where English

is spoken as a second or additional language (Yu, 2022).

Theoretical framework

The multidimensional approach, as it was first suggested by Biber in 1988, has given the current study's theoretical foundation. It is a particular strategy in methodology that is utilized for register analysis. It aids in the quantitative identification of specific linguistic co-occurrence patterns in a given language. The following six dimensions were defined by Biber (1988).

1. Involved versus Informational
2. Narrative versus Non-Narrative
3. Explicit versus Situation-Dependent
4. Abstract versus non-abstract
5. Online Informational Elaboration

(Zamna, Ahmad, Bisma, 2023), To analyze any specific genre or text type on linguistic dimensions, it is essential to understand the concept of linguistic co-occurrence. In the current study, D1 and D5 of this Multi-dimensional approach have been used to analyze the genre of written discourse in Pakistani English. We can determine where their language fits on dimensions 1 and 5 by analyzing the co-occurrence of linguistic features. It has also drawn attention to their communicational capabilities.

Methodological Framework

The data analysis was conducted using a multidimensional analytic methodology. To examine the research as specified in the question mentioned earlier, the following procedures have been conducted. The main research tool is MAT tagger software (1.3), which has been downloaded, installed, and used. In 2013, Nini created this software using Biber's (1988) framework. It just works with normal text. Using Stanford Tagger, data is annotated. It generates the file with the name MAT. Following that, the analysis procedure is performed on this tagged data. It provides details on the sizes and rankings of numerous linguistic elements. These are used to analyze the data by entering it into the software.

Data Analysis and Discussion

The desired corpus of the selected texts has been analyzed using the D1 and D5 dimensions of the multidimensional approach. This section has covered the multidimensional analysis of the written discourse in Pakistani English, D1 and D5. According to this study, a positive D1 score indicates involved and non-informational processes. For instance, this feature benefits conversation and planned presentations. The negative score on this dimension, which includes academic prose, press reports, and official papers among other things, highlights the informational and uninvolved purpose. These good and negative scores consequently have various linguistic traits. The positive side includes things like the present tense, first and second-person pronouns, private verbs, etc. (Wu, Robles, Thompson, 2024), On the other hand, nouns, attributive adjectives, and prepositional phrases are instances of language features that are detrimental. Dimension five is the division between abstract and non-abstract knowledge. High scores indicate that the text provides information in an official, technical, and abstract manner, similar to that seen, for example, in scientific speaking. There are a lot of passive sentences and conjuncts in a text with a high score on this Dimension.

Analysis of Dimension 1

The report of dimension 1 in Pakistani English Political tweets has an average of 14.74. Therefore, it receives a positive score and the genre type that most closely resembles it is personal letters.

Feature	Score
AWL (Average Word Length)	-0.32
PIN (Total Prepositional Phrase)	-0.96
NN (Nouns)	-0.17
TTR (Type-Token Ratio)	-0.36
PLACE (Place Adverbial)	0

The presence of these factors makes the text informational and non-interactive. The frequency score of prepositions is quite higher as compared to other ones. Biber's (1988) score for academic prose is -15, but the current genre score on D1 is farther away from it. The text contains a lot of prepositions and nouns which indicates that there is a lot of informational integration integrated into it. (Biber, 1988) Then, on several dimensions, both of these categories of papers have been compared to one another, and Biber's genres (1988) as a positive D1 score indicates involved and non-informational processes of information in Pakistani English tweets.

Analysis of Dimension 5

The report of dimension 5 in Pakistani English Political tweets has an average of -0.43. Therefore, it receives a negative score and the genre type that most closely resembles it is press reportage.

Text is categorized using the Dimension Five Framework according to its level of abstraction, with a particular emphasis on whether the text is abstract (high score) or not

(low score). It draws attention to the linguistic

Scores of Linguistic Features in Dimension 5	
AWL (AVERAGE WORD LENGTH)	-0.32
PIN (TOTAL PREPOSITIONAL PHRASE)	-0.96
NN (NOUNS)	-0.17
TTR (TYPE-TOKEN RATIO)	-0.36
PLACE (PLACE ADVERBIAL)	0

characteristics that correspond with each level, such as the formal style, usage of passive sentences, and technical terminology in abstract literature as opposed to more straightforward, approachable language in non-abstract works.

Analysis's Variables

This is the main variable that is of interest, the abstraction level. It gauges how abstract or specific the text's content is. Low abstraction denotes knowledge that is practical or uncomplicated, whereas high abstraction denotes theoretical or technical material. (Batool, Faqir, et. al. 2024), Passive voice usage is more common in abstract texts. Complex syntax and conjunctions are frequently used in abstract texts to communicate intricate links and ideas.

Formality of language

Compared to non-abstract literature, which tends to utilize more informal language, abstract texts frequently use formal and technical vocabulary. (Syed, Samina, Ishrat, 2023), Linguistic traits and abstraction level: Since passive voice and complex syntax (conjuncts) are common in technical or scientific writing, high abstraction is associated with these features. A concentration on practical or non-technical material is reflected in low abstraction, which is correlated with

more straightforward language and simpler sentence constructions.

Linking Analysis with the Framework

In practice, adopting this approach involves: Assessing the abstraction level of the text using quantitative or qualitative methods and recognizing linguistic features by hand inspection or text analysis technologies. (Dad, Shabbir, Sultan, et. al. 2023), Connecting these characteristics to Dimension Five's projected results, higher scores correspond to more abstract content, while lower scores correspond to less abstract or more approachable information. Utilization in Diverse Situations, Academic Prose, Because of its formal language, cerebral character, and use of passive voice, it usually receives high marks on Dimension Five.

Press Reports

(Aman, Muhammad, et. al. 2023), While scores vary, they often tend toward less abstraction and use clearer language and a more engaged voice to deliver information quickly and effectively.

Official Papers

(Irum, Shamsi, 2023), Because of their formal, technical language and complex notions, they frequently receive high scores on Dimension Five. Through comprehension and utilization of this framework, analysts can methodically classify and assess texts according to their linguistic characteristics and degree of abstraction. This methodical methodology is beneficial for both quantitative and qualitative textual content analysis.

Findings and Conclusion

The current study has concentrated on the written discourse of Pakistani English. It contains several political tweets in Pakistani English. It emphasizes how their language is complex and uninformative regarding D1. It has been demonstrated that this genre does not come near to the official language elements by comparing it to Biber's work from 1988. Additionally, the average

language used in tweets on D1 is 14.74. The D5 analysis shows that the chosen written discourse belongs to the non-abstract genre. The average statistic in this dimension is -0.43, whereas this dimension is close to press reportage. Furthermore, Pakistani tweets have nonabstract political discourse. Additionally, the study is very important for aspiring linguists working in general, and specifically in register analysis. They will be able to analyze these tweets using the additional dimensions (2, 4), as well as the other dimensions (6), of multidimensional analysis, to gain a deeper knowledge of the linguistic variances in written discourse in Pakistani English, particularly concerning the political discourse genres in that country.

The study's findings will significantly impact our understanding of Pakistani politics and society. Their insights can shed light on the people's political inclinations, the impact of language on public opinion, and the importance of register diversity in the effectiveness and reception of political discourse. (Samina, Rabia & Syed, 2023), Furthermore, this study can contribute to the field of sociolinguistics overall by shedding light on how English has altered and grown to suit different sociocultural contexts around the globe. This paper's ultimate objective is to provide a comprehensive analysis of register variety in Pakistani English political discourse. By analyzing the language choices and strategies politicians employ, this study aims to shed light on the underlying dynamics and social relevance of language in Pakistani politics. This method helps us understand the complex relationships that exist in Pakistan between language, power, and identity as well as how politics both shapes and is shaped by language.

Recommendations

The study highlights the significance of language knowledge in political tweets written in Pakistani English and stresses the necessity of communicating clearly and succinctly.

Additionally, it recommends encouraging written communication to comply with official language characteristics and align with linguistic norms. With a focus on political genres, linguists should employ multidimensional analysis to examine political tweets written in Pakistani English. Institutions ought to think about adding courses or modules dedicated to studying written discourse in Pakistani English. To add to the scholarly conversation on linguistic variety and change, more research on the dynamics of written discourse in Pakistani English is advised, especially about political discourse genres.

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